

THE INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGY ON THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: Many people use the technology for learning and teaching languages in the world, because some features of the lesson is related to only devices Maybe more and more children are addicted to technology as a local variable it can impact on their brain and physically and mentally efficient.

Key words: language learning, young people, facilities, quickly, easily, foreigners, communicate, independently and several ways.

Nowadays, language learning is widespread among young people. Many tools can effectively how productivity with learning English than other ways or methods.

The main point of learning a language with technology is to leverage digital tools and resources to enhance the effectiveness, accessibility, and personalization of language acquisition. Here are the key aspects:

1. Increased Accessibility: Technology provides learners with access to language materials, lessons, and tutors from anywhere in the world. Language learning apps, websites, and online courses allow for convenient and flexible study.

2. Personalized Learning: Many language learning platforms use algorithms to tailor lessons to individual learning styles and needs. For example, adaptive learning software adjusts content based on the learner's progress, strengths, and weaknesses.

3. Interactive and Engaging Methods: Technology introduces interactive tools like games, quizzes, and simulations that make language learning more engaging. Apps like Duolingo or Memorize gamify learning by providing rewards, levels, and challenges to motivate users.

4. Real-time Practice and Feedback: Language learners can practice speaking, writing, listening, and reading with instant feedback using apps or AI-based tools like chatbots. Speech recognition technology, for example, helps learners improve pronunciation by providing corrections in real-time.

5. Cultural Immersion: Through the internet and mobile apps, learners can access media (movies, music, articles) in the target language, allowing them to experience authentic language use in a cultural context. Tools like YouTube and language exchange platforms enable immersion in the language's natural environment.

6. Communication with Native Speakers: Technology enables language learners to connect with native speakers around the world through video conferencing (e.g., Skype, Zoom), language exchange platforms (e.g., HelloTalk, Tandem), and social media. This fosters authentic conversations and cultural exchange.

7. Autonomy and Flexibility: Learners can set their own pace, choose the content they want to focus on, and review materials whenever necessary, creating a self-directed learning experience.

8. Multimodal Learning: Technology allows for a combination of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning methods through videos, podcasts, interactive exercises, and text-based materials, which cater to different learning preferences.

CONCLUSION: In summary, technology enhances language learning by making it more accessible, personalized, interactive, and engaging, while also providing opportunities for real-time practice, cultural immersion, and communication with native speakers.

Here are more specific examples of how technology has influenced the English language:

1. Online Communication and Social Media

Slang and New Expressions: Social platforms like Twitter, TikTok, and Instagram create and spread new slang rapidly. Terms like FOMO (Fear of Missing Out), ghosting, flex, and lit originated online and are now part of everyday conversation.

Viral trends: Phrases like “break the internet”, “going viral”, and “trending” emerged from internet culture to describe widespread online popularity and have crossed into broader language usage.

2. Technological Devices and Platforms

Google as a verb: The phrase "to Google" is now synonymous with searching for information online, even if other search engines are used. For instance, "Just Google it" has become a common way of saying "look it up."

Zooming and Skyping: With the rise of virtual communication tools, terms like Zooming (using Zoom) or Skyping (using Skype) have become verbs to describe video conferencing.

3. Gaming Language

Phrases from Gaming: Terms like noob (newbie), respawn, lag, pwned, and Easter egg originated in video gaming but are now used in broader contexts. For example, "lag" can refer to any delay, not just in games.

Twitch culture: Livestreaming platforms like Twitch have influenced language with phrases like "GG" (good game), "raid" (sending viewers to another stream), and "clipping" (creating short highlight videos).

4. Digital Shortcuts

Abbreviations common in texting: Besides classic abbreviations like BRB (Be Right Back) or AFK (Away from Keyboard), new shorthand continues to emerge. For example, IDK (I Don't Know), SMH (Shaking My Head), TBH (To Be Honest), and NGL (Not Gonna Lie) are popular in both texting and social media contexts.

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